

DCC2GO

Basic Knowledge on DCCs

Information for technical staff at NMIS and DIs

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Content and goal

- These slides are intended as introduction to the Digital Calibration Certificate (DCC) for technical experts.
- The purpose is to support the implementation of DCCs within the European metrology community by providing knowledge on technical specifications for practitioners in metrology and IT information
- The slides are part of a knowledge compendium also containing a common introduction to DCCs and more specific information for management and stakeholders of NMIs and DIs

Today's production life cycle

Life cycle of “calibration – use – recalibration” of measuring equipment

figure: S. Hackel, et al, PTB, 2019

Today's production life cycle

NMI & DI (calibration laboratory) start of working with DCCs

figure: S. Hackel, et al, PTB, 2019

DCC examples

DCC by XML document

- Fully XML structured file with all calibration information and data in machine-readable format
- Optional human readable file (such as PDF) included as binary machine-readable data

DCC by PDF document

- PDF document providing human readable information and containing
- Additional machine readable files with calibration result data

Example: XML Type DCC (1/3)

Fundamental XML DCC-layout

- 1. Administrative shell (mainly regulated by ISO/IEC 17025)
- 2. Calibration results (partly regulated by ISO/IEC 17025)
- 3. Individual information (not regulated)
- 4. Optional Attachment:
„Human readable document“ (e. g. PDF)

+ Framework conditions
+ legal requirements

Figure from SmartCom project, DOI:10.5281/zenodo.3696567

Example: XML Type DCC (2/3)

Digital Calibration Certificate

Administrative Data

Unique Identifier	DCC2GO-Temperature-DCC-Example
Issuer	calibrationLaboratory
Order no.	2023/04/0001
Performance Date	2023-04-13 to 2023-04-14
Performance Location	laboratory

Items	
• Item	Temperature sensor
Manufacturer	Sensor-Manufacturer
Model	PT100
Issuer	manufacturer
Serial no.	2309823482

Calibration Laboratory	
E-Mail	EMPIR-DCC2GO
E-Mail	dcc2go@ptb.de
City	Capital City
Post Code	12345
Street	High Street
Street No.	1
Further	https://www.ptb.de/dcc2go/project

Person(s) authorizing the report		
Name	Jane Bloggs	true
Main signer		

Customer	Example Company
E-Mail	info@customer.xx
City	Capital City
Post Code	789101

Human-readable
to
machine-readable

1/3

<XML/>

DCC

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="utf-8"?>
<dcc:digitalCalibrationCertificate
  xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance"
  xmlns:dcc="https://ptb.de/dcc"
  xmlns:si="https://ptb.de/si"
  xsi:schemaLocation="https://ptb.de/dcc https://ptb.de/dcc/v3.2.0/dcc.xsd"
  schemaVersion="3.2.0">
  <dcc:administrativeData>
    <dcc:dccSoftware>
    <dcc:coreData>
      <dcc:countryCodeISO3166_1>GB</dcc:countryCodeISO3166_1>
      <dcc:usedLangCodeISO639_1>en</dcc:usedLangCodeISO639_1>
      <dcc:mandatoryLangCodeISO639_1>en</dcc:mandatoryLangCodeISO639_1>
      <dcc:uniqueIdentifier>DCC2GO-Temperature-DCC-Example</dcc:uniqueIdentifier>
      <dcc:identifications>
      <dcc:beginPerformanceDate>2023-04-13</dcc:beginPerformanceDate>
      <dcc:endPerformanceDate>2023-04-14</dcc:endPerformanceDate>
      <dcc:performanceLocation>laboratory</dcc:performanceLocation>
    </dcc:coreData>
    <dcc:items>
    <dcc:calibrationLaboratory>
    <dcc:respPersons>
    <dcc:customer>
    <dcc:statements>
  </dcc:administrativeData>
  <dcc:measurementResults>
  <dcc:document>
</dcc:digitalCalibrationCertificate>
```

DCC2GO-Temperature-DCC-Example.pdf

DCC2GO-Temperature-DCC-Example.xml

Example: XML Type DCC (3/3)

Measuring results			
Reference value	[degreecelsius]		
33.098			
99.971			
175.103			
250.169			
320.004			
Indicated measured value probe			
[degreecelsius]			
33.17			
100.06			
175.21			
250.16			
319.92			
Measurement error			
[kelvin]			
0.072			
0.089			
0.107			
-0.009			
-0.084			
Uncertainty List	Coverage Factor List	Coverage Probability List	Distribution List
[kelvin]			
0.061	2	0.95	normal

Human-readable
to
machine-readable

```

<XML/>
DCC
<dcc:measurementResult>
  <dcc:results>
    <dcc:result refType="dcc2go exampleMeasuringResult">
      <dcc:data>
        <dcc:list refType="dcc2go exampleTable">
          <dcc:quantity refType="basic_referenceValue">
            <si:realListXMLList>
              <si:valueXMLList>33.098 99.971 175.103 250.169 320.004</si:valueXMLList>
              <si:unitXMLList>\degreecelsius</si:unitXMLList>
            </si:realListXMLList>
          </dcc:quantity>
          <dcc:quantity refType="basic_measuredValue">
            <si:realListXMLList>
              <si:valueXMLList>33.17 100.06 175.21 250.16 319.92</si:valueXMLList>
              <si:unitXMLList>\degreecelsius</si:unitXMLList>
            </si:realListXMLList>
          </dcc:quantity>
          <dcc:quantity refType="basic_measurementError">
            <si:realListXMLList>
              <si:valueXMLList>0.072 0.089 0.107 -0.009 -0.084</si:valueXMLList>
              <si:unitXMLList>\kelvin</si:unitXMLList>
              <si:expandedUncXMLList>
                <si:uncertaintyXMLList>0.061</si:uncertaintyXMLList>
                <si:coverageFactorXMLList>2</si:coverageFactorXMLList>
                <si:coverageProbabilityXMLList>0.95</si:coverageProbabilityXMLList>
                <si:distributionXMLList>normal</si:distributionXMLList>
              </si:expandedUncXMLList>
            </si:realListXMLList>
          </dcc:quantity>
        </dcc:list>
      </dcc:data>
    </dcc:result>
  </dcc:results>
</dcc:measurementResult>
    
```

IT Requirements

Start working with XML type DCCs

- An office computer is sufficient to start reading and writing XML DCCs
- People experienced with XML may use **standard text & code editors** such as Notepad, Notepad++, Visual Studio
- PTB offers the **GEMIMEG TOOL** which is a prototype web service for creating and reading DCCs with a user interface for people without experience in XML. The XML is created by the web service

A screenshot of the GEMIMEG TOOL web interface. The browser address bar shows 'https://www.gemimeg.ptb.de/gemimeg-tool/#/'. The page title is 'Administrative Data'. There are two main sections: 'Used Software' and 'Core Data'. The 'Used Software' section contains a table with columns 'Name', 'Version', 'Description', and 'Actions'. One entry is 'Notepad++ (32-bit)' with version 'v8.2'. The 'Core Data' section has a 'Country Code' dropdown menu set to 'DE - Germany'. At the bottom, there are 'PREVIOUS STEP' and 'NEXT STEP' buttons. On the right side, there is a 'Language selection for datasets' section with 'EN' and 'DE' options, and a vertical navigation menu with steps: 1 Administrative Data, 2 Items, 3 Statements, and 4 Measurement Results.

Official documentation and resources:

<https://www.ptb.de/dcc/>

https://dccwiki.ptb.de/en/DCC_basic_ideas

Example: PDF/A-3 Type DCC (1/2)

Fundamental PDF/A-3 DCC layout

1. PDF/A-3 File

2. Embedded (attached) machine-readable files

Community specific files appended, not regulated

Example: PDF/A-3 Type DCC (2/2)

Appended machine-readable files

```
DCC2GO-Temperature-DCC-Example.xml
1 <?xml version="1.0" encoding="utf-8"?>
2 <dcc:digitalCalibrationCertificate xmlns:
  "http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance" xmlns:dcc="https://ptb.de/dcc"
  xmlns:si="https://ptb.de/si" xsi:schemaLocation="https://ptb.de/dcc
  https://ptb.de/dcc/v3.2.0/dcc.xsd" schemaVersion="3.2.0">
3
4   <dcc:administrativeData>
5     <dcc:dccSoftware>
6       <dcc:software>
7         <dcc:name>
8           <dcc:content>GEMIMEG tool</dcc:content>
9         </dcc:name>
```

XML DCC file

```
DCC2GO-Temperature-DCC-Example.json
1 {
2   "dcc:digitalCalibrationCertificate":
3
4   {
5     "@xmlns:dcc": "https://ptb.de/dcc",
6     "@xmlns:si": "https://ptb.de/si",
7     "@xmlns:xsi": "http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance",
8     "@xsi:schemaLocation": "https://ptb.de/dcc
9     https://ptb.de/dcc/v3.2.0/dcc.xsd",
10    "@dcc:schemaVersion": "3.2.0",
11    "dcc:administrativeData": {
```

JSON file with calibration data

```
hash.dat
1 #1
2 filename 'DCC2GO-Temperature-DCC-Example.json'
3 hash_sha-256 '20e18894ab6f070aa0ca27e29bef8977b3ebd76a365b4e79b7b8848fc7832f01'
4
5 #2
6 filename 'DCC2GO-Temperature-DCC-Example.xml'
7 hash_sha-256 '6ada211c156383e7b03680fb4fdbccff220e09a28cc62034f196fbf6a7f40a23b'
```

file with SHA-256 hash values

human-readable

Digital Calibration Certificate

Administrative Data

DCC Software

- Software Name: GEMIMEG tool
- Release: v1.3.0

Core Data

- Country Code ISO3166_1: GB
- Used Language Code ISO639_1: en
- Mandatory Language Code ISO639_1: en
- Unique Identifier: DCC2GO-Temperature-DCC-Example
- Issuer: calibrationLaboratory
- Order no.: 2023/04/0001
- Performance Date: 2023-04-13 to 2023-04-14
- Performance Location: laboratory

Items

- Item: Temperature sensor
- Manufacturer: Sensor-Manufacturer
- Model: PT100
- Issuer: manufacturer
- Serial no.: 2309823482

Calibration Laboratory

- EMPIR-DCC2GO
- E-Mail: dcc2go@ptb.de
- City: Capital City
- Post Code: 12345
- Street: High Street
- Street No.: 1
- Further: https://www.ptb.de/dcc2go/project

Person(s) authorizing the report

- Name: Jane Bloggs
- Main signer: true

Customer

- Example Company
- E-Mail: info@customer.xx
- City: Capital City
- Post Code: 789101

Anlagen

- DCC2GO-Temperature-DCC-Example.json
- DCC2GO-Temperature-DCC-Example.xml
- hash.dat

eExample-DCC2GO.pdf

IT Requirements

Start working with PDF/A-3 type DCCs

- An office computer is sufficient to start creating a PDF/A-3 DCC.
- In many cases, only professional PDF creation software provide the tools to properly create the PDF/A-3 without manual coding.
- **METAS eCertificate** is an open source prototype tool for creating a PDF/A-3u DCC based on a LaTeX template. Usage of this tool requires the ability to use LaTeX.

Documentation and resources:

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.measen.2021.100282>

<https://github.com/wollmich/metas-ecertificate>

Today's production life cycle

NMI & DI (calibration laboratory) start of working with DCCs

figure: S. Hackel, et al, PTB, 2019

Today's production life cycle

NMI & DI (calibration laboratory) advancing DCC transfer

figure: S. Hackel, et al, PTB, 2019

Role of digital signatures and seals

Providing DCC Integrity
(no modifications)

Providing DCC Authenticity
(from our "lab")

Correct DCC from the Calibration Laboratory

Confidential transmission
(encryption)

IT Requirements

Start working with electronic and digital signatures

- **An office computer is sufficient** to start working with electronic and digital signatures
- Most **PDF viewing and editing software allows to create simple electronic signatures** that allow a low level protection of PDF documents against manipulation.
- **Qualified digital signatures** for documents (XML, PDF, ...) and document containers (folders) are more advanced and start working with this will need additional equipment:
 - Software to apply signature to files
 - Private (secret) digital key code for signing on a key card
 - Hardware device connected to computer via USB for reading the key card and authorising signature

The European Commission has a list of providers of trusted and recognized signatures

<https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/eu-trusted-lists>

Today's production life cycle

NMI & DI (calibration laboratory) advancing automation of DCC creation

figure: S. Hackel, et al, PTB, 2019

Today's production life cycle

NMI & DI (calibration laboratory) advancing automation of DCC usage

figure: S. Hackel, et al, PTB, 2019

IT Requirements

- Some areas of a organization may already have laboratories where software and IT infrastructure has been established that allows an automatic processing of a calibration and the automatic creation of the Calibration Certificate (Word, PDF, or similar). Automatically creating a DCC would require only an additional output module for the software.
- **General requirements comprise for example**
 - Databases for storing measurement data, calibration data, administrative data for customers, equipment data, etc.
 - Data exchange network allowing data exchange between digital outputs of measuring devices and software running the calibration (including instruments able to send and receive data)
 - Software automating the calibration process (controlling devices etc., collecting and evaluating data as well as creating output reports)

In case of the XML type DCC, first commercial tools are available

Today's production life cycle

NMI & DI (calibration laboratory) advancing automation of services

© figure: S. Hackel, et al, PTB, 2019

IT Requirements

- Calibration laboratory and customer will need access to the world wide web to be able to exchange relevant information
- The calibration laboratory needs to operate an access point for customers, e.g., an application running on a web server (hosted or rent by laboratory) or an service establish through a cloud environment.
- The service of the calibration laboratory could provide a Web Page for humans to manually enter and submit data and in addition have a programming interface through which software of a customer could automatically submit data.
- The customer may need to register an account at the service provided by the laboratory to be enabled to digitally submit requests for calibration.
- The customer may operate an equipment management system that automatically schedules and requests re-calibration.

Machine-Interoperability

“Bad analogue data will create bad digital data”

Automation of processes and usage of data by machines will **need machine-interoperable data ready for human-to-machine and machine-to-machine communication**

Developments towards wider machine-interoperable DCCs include

- Harmonization of formats like XML DCC
- Harmonization of domain (measurand) specific calibration results & good practices
- Harmonization of common identifiers (terms) for data and properties in DCCs
- Where different DCC types are used, software for mapping between different data representations

Harmonization examples:

CIPM Digital-SI (format, SI identifiers) **DKD committees** (domain, good practice, identifiers)

XML DCC (format, identifiers) **EURAMET TC-IM 1448 DCC** (good practice, identifiers, mappings)

Credits

21SCP01 DCC2GO

Supporting the implementation of Digital Calibration Certificates in the European metrology community

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Coordinator Anke Keidel (PTB)

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